

MONITORING AND REPAIR TECHNIQUE FOR INTERFACIAL DE-BONDING IN CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS BY MEANS OF INDUCTION HEATING

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Keywords: Induction heating, MHz frequency, Interfacial de-bonding, Re-welding, Non-destructive monitoring

ABSTRACT

In injection molded parts of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites (CFRTPs), interface between carbon fiber and matrix resin plays an important role on the performance of the molded parts. In this study, a novel method by using MHz-frequency induction heating was proposed to repair and monitor interfacial debonding in injection molded parts. Direct heating of carbon fibers in CF/PP composites by means of MHz-frequency induction was applied to re-weld between fiber and matrix resin. Flexural properties of specimens with and without induction heating were examined in order to see whether the interfacial strength between fiber and matrix resin recover by heating. As the result, it came clear that carbon direct heating resulted in increase of bending modulus. Observation by SEM proved that induction heating improved the interfacial condition and the increase in bending modulus was closely related with the interfacial bonding improvement. It was also proved by consecutively repeated heating that temperature rise on the surface of specimens after each heating varied depending on bonding state at the interface with reflecting the difference in heat transfer at the interface between heating fiber and resin. Finally, the same method used for repair of the interface debonding can also be available to detect the interfacial bonding status.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites (CFRTPs) are hopeful candidates for fast-rate and flexible production and prototyping of high strength light weight members. By means of stamping press and injection molding, high productivity can be achieved. On the other hand, defects such as non-impregnation of matrix resin or voids resulted from high viscosity of molten matrix resins will be generated in molded or pressed articles. Actually it was reported that considerable amount of void in injection molded parts was observed by X-ray CT inspection [1]. In addition interfacial debonding between fiber and matrix resin is also possible to occur accompanied with shrinkage of the matrix resin during solidification or shaping. Integral molding of large scale parts is tried to reduce a cost for manufacturing. As the larger molded parts become, the more defects such as mentioned can be generated. Unless effective repair techniques are developed, the limited defective leads to whole disposition of large integrally molded CFRTP articles. Moreover, it is very hard to detect the interfacial debonding compared with non-impregnation or void. To utilize CFRTPs industrially monitoring technique for thin openings like the interfacial debonding is inevitable.

Many studied have been performed to detect such thin opening [2]. Among them it is reported that pulse thermography is applicable to detect inter-laminar delamination. But its application is limited near the surface and its resolution is not enough to detect interfacial debonding between fiber and matrix resin in injection molded or stamp pressed parts [3].

We have developed a monitoring method by using high-frequency induction heating to detect

difference in fiber conditions (fraction, length and orientation etc.) in injection molded parts [4]. Induction heating of carbon-fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites is developed for welding and attains some useful results [5]. Composites with continuous carbon-fibers usually used in those studies are well heated by the induction of the frequency below some hundred kHz, but injection molded composites with separated discontinuous fiber cannot be heated by induction of the such frequency.

In this study we propose a novel technique for monitoring and repair the interfacial debonding in injection molded parts by induction heating of MHz frequency, which enable to melt the resin just in the vicinity of the fiber very rapidly. The mechanical properties after the induction heating were examined by bending compared with those as injection molded without induction heating. SEM observation of fracture surface after bending tests was carried out for the specimens to see whether the interface was re-welded or not. It was discussed whether change in bending properties by induction heating resulted from re-welding at the interface and coincided with the observed interfacial bonding state by SEM.

In order to confirm repairing result this technique is also tried to apply to monitoring interfacial debonding. Noticing that temperature rise on the specimen surface during induction reflects heat transfer from carbon fiber to matrix resin, consecutively repeated heating was carried out to see how the rising curve of temperature on the surface varied with heating times. The change in the surface temperature curve was examined whether it reflected the interfacial bonding state, together with the flexural properties by bending tests and SEM observation.

2. MECHANISM OF REPAIR AND MONITORING INTERFACIAL DEBONDING BY INDUCTION HAETING

To repair interfacial debonding not only melting of matrix resin but also pressing the molten matrix resin against fiber at the interface are inevitable. As shown in Figure 1, local expansion of molten matrix resin caused by very rapid heating is supposed to be effective to attain such pressing. Induction heating is demonstrated for rapid heating of continuous carbon-fiber and its composites. But it is hard to heat discontinuous short carbon-fibers scattered separately like those in injection molded parts. Hence the inductive heat generation is proportional to the frequency squared, induction of MHz frequency is employed in this study to heat very rapidly the discontinuous fibers in injection molded parts. This resulted in local melting of the matrix resin only in the vicinity of the heated fiber. Following rapid expansion of the molten resin will act as high pressure on the interface by constrain of the surrounding solid state resin. The small volume of heated and molten resin results in rapid cooling and solidification, so it is possible to shorten cycle time for repair. Such similar mechanism is proposed in laser welding between plastic resin and metal which achieved high bond strength [6]. Localized heating and cooling could be considered to be effective for re-bonding of interfacial debonding between fiber and matrix resin.

Figure 1: Repair mechanism of interfacial debonding by induction heating.

Concerning about monitoring for interfacial debonding, temperature on the surface varies depending on heat conduction path from the heating fibers to the surface as shown in Figure 2. If there are air gaps between the fiber and matrix resin caused by interfacial debonding, the temperature on the surface arises more slowly compared with the case without interfacial debonding. Temperature rise on the surface can reflect the bonding state at the interface, so the slower temperature rise means presence

of interfacial debonding. By noticing temperature rise on the surface, the same method as that employed in the repair of interfacial debonding is also available for monitoring welded status at the interface and check of repair completion.

Figure 2: Temperature rise curve on surface with and without interfacial debonding.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

3.1 Materials and Specimens

Materials used in injection molding are carbon-fiber/PP pellets in which weight fraction of carbon fiber are 10%, 20% and 30% (PYROFIL PP-C-10A, PP-C-20A, PP-C-30A Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd.). Plates as shown in Figure 3 were molded using a mold with a film gate to align the fibers by an injection molding machine (NEX110-12E Nissei Plastic Industrial Co., Ltd.). Strips of 25 mm width were cut out from the plates as shown in Figure 3, as that the longitudinal direction of the strip intersects the injection direction, i.e. fiber orientation. It is because interfacial bonding state will be clearly reflected with bending properties.

3.2 Induction heating

The induction heating experiments were performed with an induction generator of the frequency of 2 MHz and the power of 5 kW (IH-052W, IH-052M-FC YS Electric Industry Co., Ltd.), which is newly developed by using MOS-FET [7]. The coil has cylindrical shape of double turn with 30 mm in inner diameter. The strip-shape specimen was positioned below the coil at the distance of 1mm with its center being matched with the coil center. The temperature in the central part of about 8 mm in diameter on the specimen surface faced on the coil side was measured by a pyrometer (FT-H20 Keyence Co., Ltd.). The experimental setup is shown in Figure 4. The heating was controlled by ranging the generator voltage between 90 V and 130 V, while the heating duration was kept constant of 300 seconds.

Figure 3: Specimen cut out from injected plate.

Figure 4: Induction heating set-up.

3.3 Bending tests and SEM observation of fracture surface

All specimens with and without induction heating were tested by a 3-point bending with a span of 60 mm. Bending tests were performed with the injection direction of the specimen set perpendicularly to the tensile stress and the heated portion located just below the loading indenter. Bending moduli were obtained using strain gages of gage length of 2 mm adhered on the tensile surface of the specimens.

Fracture surface after the bending test was observed by a low vacuum SEM (Hitachi High-Technologies Corp. S-3000N) without deductive coating.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Heating at different generator voltages and flexural properties

As a first step, the specimens of CF fraction of 20 wt% were heated with at three different generator voltages of 90 V, 110 V and 130 V to investigate the influence of heating rate and achieved temperature on flexural properties. Figure 5 shows the temperature curves on the specimen surface during induction heating. Heating rates and achieved temperatures vary with the generator voltage. In the figure the maximum and the minimum heating curves are plotted for each generator voltage and repeatability of the heating is almost 10 °C at most.

Fig. 6 shows the bending moduli of the specimens which were heated at different voltages. In the same figure modulus of the specimens as injection molded is also shown for comparison. It can be observed that the specimens heated at higher voltage, i.e., faster heating rate and higher achieved temperature, show higher bending modulus. The bending modulus of the specimens heated at 130 V increases of 27 % compared with that of the as-injected specimens without heating. As for the bending strength, the specimens heated at 90 V shows almost the same strength but those heated at 110 V and 130 V show decreased strength compared with that of the as-injected specimen.

In Figure 7, SEM photos of fracture surface after bending tests are shown for a specimen heated at generator volt of 90V. Figure 7 (a) is the fracture surface of the specimen as injection molded and Figure 7 (b) is that of the specimen with induction heating. Some differences at the interface between fiber and matrix are observed between Figures 7 (a) and (b). Gaps between fiber and matrix are observed in Figure 7 (a) but less gaps are observed in Figure 7 (b). With paying the attention to the surface of pulled-out fibers smooth surface was shown in Figure 7 (a). On the other hand it was observed in Figure 7 (b) that the matrix resin adhered on the pulled-out fibers. Combined with the result that the bending moduli increased after induction heating as shown in Figure 6 (a), matrix resin around the fibers is considered to be melted and re-welded with fibers by induction heating. The increase in bonding area at the fiber and matrix interface leads to improvement in bending modulus.

Figure 5: Heating curves of 20wt%CF/PP at induction voltage of 90V, 110V and 130V.

Figure 6: Flexural properties of 20 wt% CF/PP heated at voltage of 90V, 110V and 130V.

Figure 7: SEM photos of fracture surface of 20 wt% CF/PP specimen (a) without and (b) with induction heating at voltage of 90 V.

4.2 Heating of different CF fraction specimens and their flexural properties

As a second step, experiments at a constant generator power 90 V using three different CF fraction specimens of 10 wt%, 20 wt% and 30 wt% were performed to investigate the influence of heating mass on flexural properties. Figure 8 shows the temperature curves on the specimen surface during induction heating. Both heating rates and achieved temperatures on the surface varied according to the CF fraction. The more CF fraction, i.e. more heating fibers and less heated matrix resin, resulted in the faster heating rate and the higher achieved temperature on the surface.

Figure 9 shows bending moduli and bending strengths before and after the heating in comparison. The bending moduli increased with CF fraction except for the result of 10 wt% in which temperature rise was not observed. The increase rate in bending modulus is higher in the specimens of 30 wt% CF than in those of 20 wt% CF (Figure 6 (a)). The higher heating rate and the higher reached temperature attain the more increase in bending modulus similarly as the result shown in Figure 6 (a) obtained from the different heating voltage experiments.

On the other hand, concerning the bending strength it decreases in the specimens of 30 wt% CF after heating compared with that of the as-injected specimen without heating. Contrarily the strength of the 20 wt% CF specimen showed almost the same bending strength even after heating. Similar result was obtained in the experiments with different heating voltages as shown in Figure 6 (b). The bending strength of the specimen heated with 130 V showed almost the same tendency as that of the 30 wt% CF specimen. Noticing that the surface temperature of the 30 wt% CF specimen is almost the same as that of the 20 wt% CF specimen heated at 130 V, over-heating above a certain temperature is supposed to cause a lowering of bending strength compared to the as-injection molded specimens.

Figure 8: Temperature rising curves during induction heating for different CF fractions.

Figure 9: Flexural properties of specimens with and without IH for different CF fractions.

4.3 Consecutively repeated heating and flexural properties after each heating times

SEM observation proved that gaps existed at the interface between fiber and matrix resin could influence on the flexural modulus. As another method to detect debonding at the interface, heat transfer was noticed and consecutively repeated heating experiments were performed. Heating was repeated to the same specimen after the heated specimen cooled and surface temperature curve at each heating was examined by comparing with each other. Because air gaps at the interface prevent heat transfer from heating fiber to matrix resin, temperature rising rate on the specimen surface can reflect the existence of air gaps, i.e. debonding, at the interface.

Figure 10 shows heating curves on the surface measured in three times repeated heating experiments. Specimens used were those of 20 wt% CF and voltage of the generator was 90 V. The first heating curve in Figure 10 is that obtained during heating the as-injection molded specimen. Second heating curve is obtained from the same specimen after once heating and cooling. From the heating curves showed in Figure 10, it was observed that the rising rate and the fluctuated temperature were getting higher as the heating was repeated. And it is also observed that the increment in rising rate and reached temperature is getting saturated with repeated times.

In Figure 11, flexural properties obtained from the specimens after each times of heating are shown together with those of as-injected specimens. From Figure 11, bending modulus increases considerably after the first heating procedure. The increment in the bending modulus saturated and the bending modulus reached almost a constant value after the second heating. This change in bending modulus shows the same tendency as observed in heating curves in Figure 10. Taking it into account that heating curves reflect the heat conductivity at the interface as mentioned in above, the higher

temperature rising rate and the higher reached temperature appear as a result of the less gaps at the interface. It is reasonable to consider that the increase both in the temperature elevation rate and the bending modulus resulted from re-bonding at the interface. From the surface temperature curve and the flexural test results repair of the debonding at the interface was almost completed during the first heating.

About bending strength it was observed that the bending strength showed almost the same up till second heating but it got smaller after third heating. Based on the result about bending strength in section 4.1 and 4.2 excessive inputted heat is considered to cause degradation of the matrix resin and result in decrease in the bending strength.

Figure 10: Temperature rise curves by consecutively repeated heating of 20 wt% CF/PP.

Figure 11: Flexural properties after each heating times in consecutively repeated heating.

To check the bonding state at the interface SEM observation was performed for the bending tested specimens. Photos of the fracture surface after each consecutive heating were shown in Figure 12. In the photos it was proved that fracture surface of the specimen after once heating was considerably different with that of the as-injected specimen and the difference after the second heating is hardly observed. In Figure 12 (b)-(d) which are the photos of fracture surface with heating, it looks like that resin portion increases and fibers are embedded in the matrix resin compared with the fracture surface of as-inject specimen shown in Figure 11(a). The interface condition observed in the SEM photos are well coincided with the heating curves and the bending moduli and supported the change in the heating curves and the bending moduli.

Figure 12: SEM photos of fracture surface after each heating in consecutively repeated heating.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, repair technique for interfacial debonding between fiber and matrix resin in carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites (CFRTPs) was proposed. MHz frequency induction heating was employed to heat carbon fibers rapidly. The efficiency of this method for repair of interfacial debonding was examined by bending tests and SEM observation. Heating of carbon fiber in CFRTPs by MHz frequency generator resulted in increase in bending modulus and SEM observation supported that the result of the bending modulus increase came from interfacial re-bonding.

In addition, the same method was applied to determine progress of the repair at the interface, with noticing that the temperature on the specimen surface reflected the heat transfer from the heating fiber to matrix resin. In consecutively repeated heating, temperature rising curve on the surface varied at each time of heating, and the rising rate and reached temperature were well correlative with the bending modulus and SEM observation of bonding state at the interface. Temperature curve on the surface during multiple times induction heating was proved to be used as a monitor of repair progress by seeing whether temperature response saturated in repeated heating.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge Dr. Y. Sugita, the president of YS Electric Industry Co., Ltd. for the corporation and helpful discussion about induction heating of CFRTPs.

REFERENCES

- [1] <http://www.an.shimadzu.co.jp/products/general/pdf/c10g-0051.pdf>
- [2] A. Benammara, R. Draia, A. Guessoumb, Detection of delamination defects in CFRP materials using ultrasonic signal processing, *Ultrasonics*, **48**, 2008, pp. 731–738.
- [3] B.B. Lahiri, S. Bagavathiappan, P.R. Reshmi, J. Philip, T. Jayakumar, B. Raj, Quantification of defects in composites and rubber materials using active thermography, *Infrared Physics & Technology*, **55**, 2012, pp.191–199.
- [4] K. Takenaka, T. Miyake, M. Niikawa, Monitoring technique using direct heating of fibers for fiber length and dispersion in injection molded CFRTP parts, *Proceedings of M&M 2013, Gifu, Japan, Oct. 12-14, 2013*, Japan Society of Mech. Eng., Paper OS2007.
- [5] T.J. Ahmed, D. Stavrov, H.E.N. Bersee, A. Beukers, Induction welding of thermoplastic composites – an overview, *Composites: Part A*, **37**, 2006, pp.1638-1651.
- [6] Japan Patent JP 4873482, 2012.
- [7] <http://ysel.jp/product1.html>